

CAREGIVERSPRO
MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: A European platform to support people living with dementia and their caregivers

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26th Alzheimer Europe Conference,
Copenhagen, November 2016

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This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211

Project identity card

Consortium

- H2020 Project (H2020-PHC-2015-25)
- Grant Agreement: 690211
- Research and Innovation action
- Start: January 1st, 2016
- Duration: 36 months
- Target groups: People with dementia, Mild cognitive impairment, informal caregivers

The aim of the project is to create an digital platform for people with dementia (PwD) or Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and their caregivers that will provide services based on social networks, tailored interventions, clinical strategies and gamification in order to improve quality of life, wellbeing and medication compliance.

Background

- Cost effective interventions (Blom et al., 2013)
- Information and Communication Technology (ICT)
- Web-based educational programs (Cristancho-Lacroix et al., 2015)
- Digital platforms with social interventions/forums (Torkamani et al., 2014)

Background

- Quality of life
- Caregiver burden
- Depression
- Anxiety & Stress

<http://scdigitalhealth.com/about/>

Aims & Objectives

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform

- Combination of ICT interventions

PwD

- Quality of Life
- Activities of Daily Living
- Treatment Adherence
- Depression
- Anxiety
- Neuropsychological Functioning
- Number of hospitalizations
- Reduce care costs

Caregivers

- Burden
- Treatment adherence
- Quality of Life
- Social Support

Dyad

- Quality of relationship

Methods

Platform services

- Social network
- Fora
- Reminders for medication
- Information about medication (side effects)
- Localised information (support & events)
- Online questionnaires
- Educational Information
- Monitored by healthcare professionals
- Gamification

Methods

Participants

- 600 dyads (PwD and caregivers)

Country	Partner	Number of dyads
Spain	FUB	200
Italy	COOSS	200
United Kingdom	UoH	100
France	CHU	100

Inclusion & exclusion criteria

- MCI, mild, mild to moderate dementia
- 50 years old
- Informal caregiver

Procedure

- Tablet & platform access
- Training
- 18 months – May 2017
- 6-month research visits

Expected benefits for stakeholders

PwD or MCI

- **Personalised care plan**, offering a combination of medication, behavioural and alternative treatment optimised to their personal needs. Constant monitoring **to indicate changes** in well-being, allowing **fast adjustment of care plan**.

Caregivers

- Reduce caregiving time spent. **Support by professionals** to manage carer's own mental and physical well-being. **Reduce caregivers' stress and burden**.

Expected benefits for stakeholders

Healthcare professionals

- **Reduce time** spent on administration (ie data collection). **Improve decision-making** for treatment, based on behavioural, medical, psychological and social changes, allowing future improvement in care plans interventions.

Social worker professionals

- **Better understanding** of users' behavioural changes and social participation. **Monitor** PwD/MCI and caregivers' interaction and engagement in society.

Expected benefits for stakeholders

Overall healthcare system

- Reduce or delay hospitalisations or admission to care homes for PwD/MCI

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Caregiverspro-Mmd project

@Caregiverspromd

CAREGIVERSPRO_MMD Project (group)

<http://dziraaquaponique.blogspot.co.uk/?view=snapshot>

<http://caregiversprommd-project.eu/>

Thank you

Any questions?

References

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- Blom MM, Bosmans JE, Cuijpers P, *et al.* 2013. Effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of an internet intervention for family caregivers of people with dementia: design of a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Psychiatry* **13**: 17.
- Cristancho-Lacroix V, Wrobel J, Cantegreil-Kallen I, *et al.* 2015. A Web-Based Psychoeducational Program for Informal Caregivers of Patients With Alzheimer's Disease: A Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Med Internet Res* **17**: e117.
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